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RULES OF NATIONAL MUSIC EDUCATION IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS

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Annotation: *Achievements in national music activities in educational institutions are inextricably linked with school life. Today's self-awareness is an opportunity to create our own destiny and the future of our children. first and foremost is to know our history well. Because every innovation is made through a historical connection.*

Key words: *music education, shashmaqom, popular melodies, folklore.*

The introduction of state educational standards in music education, as in all disciplines, will allow to make full use of the national musical heritage. These are reflected in the creative activities of singers and musicians from popular melodies and songs, maqom, shoshmaqom, epics and contemporary music. Such opportunities in the art of music serve as a unique source of education for the new generation and their harmonious development. The new content of music education on the basis of state educational standards, along with musical knowledge and skills of students, provides them with the development of observation, memory, imagery, creativity, independence, initiative, artistic and musical taste. This means that "Music Culture" is very important in educating the younger generation.

National music education has a creative impact on the moral and aesthetic education of students. It instills in them a sense of beauty, arouses love and interest in the art of music, teaches them to love the motherland, respect each other, adults, love and appreciate nature, helps you find your place in life. The main goal of music education is to teach students the art of music in all its nuances, to understand music, to sing and dance individually and in groups, to develop creative skills. It is also the task of music education to create the necessary conditions for the development of students' talents and to meet their artistic needs. Modern music is a function of education. Modern music education shows that music lessons and the system of extracurricular music education play an important role in the study of our national musical heritage. It needs to be integrated with the education system.

Modern technologies for the spiritual development of the teacher, in particular, practical lessons on the effective use of the Internet, extracurricular activities, mainly in the appropriate use of national values in the education of young people, so I recommend the following:

- The national nature of the specific forms, methods and means of activities;
- Achieving freedom, humanism and focus on skill in the event;
- The content, richness, historical place and significance of the traditions of the region where young people live;
- Creating the image of our ancestors in additional classes;
- the use of exemplary proverbs, hadiths and phrases encouraging goodness, rich in spiritual heritage;
- study of folklore;

We know that elementary school students, even when they are young, have a passion for learning about life, so the teacher needs to focus on the level of activities planned. The pedagogical significance of these factors, taking into account its specific features and circumstances, enhances our national values and plays an important role among young people in the study of the system of traditions. As Uzbeks are a childish people, they always call for discipline and advice, no matter who their children are. Elementary school activities are also highly educational. Each event will have its own purpose, a great idea, and songs and melodies that will create an artistic quality accordingly.

All forms of singing, music, dance, and folklore are used during the event. In particular, all the events held in secondary schools, ie the New Year, Defender of the Fatherland Day, International Women's Day, Navruz, Independence Day, except for the main holidays and events of the public education system, which are the first bell, teachers and coaches day, the last bell is among them. The songs "Muchal Toi", "Hosil Bayrami" and "Mehrjon" of the independence period are also sung.

The songs "Oyijon", "Chamandagul", "Soglom avlod", "Vatanginam", "Tinchlik", "Tanovar", "Dilxiroj", "Joy", "Cotton", "Puppet", Perform dances "Andijan regiment". By using DVDs, VSDs, and computers to engage students in the activities listed, the knowledge and level of knowledge will be formed and the thinking range of the growing children will be broadened and enriched spiritually.

Primary school students should also be taught to remember the past, with the teacher inviting veterans of labor, participants of the Great Patriotic War, relatives of deceased teachers to the events dedicated to the "Day of Remembrance and Honor": "Dear compatriots, you are always in our hearts!" such as a theatrical art night. Poems

commemorating the spirit of the past are widely used. Heavy - heavy, national classical melodies are used.

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